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Application of TOPSIS to the Selection of Project Execution Options in the Maritime Sector of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

In maritime sector of Nigeria, several techniques are employed to award contract. The alternatives of awarding contracts considered in this research are direct labour, local firms, foreign firms, combination of direct labour and local firm, combination of direct labour and foreign firm, and combination of local firm and foreign firm. The five criteria used for the selection are project cost, quality of project, project delivery time, impact of project execution on the economy and acceptability of the project by the locals. TOPSIS approach was applied to select the best alternative based on the five stated criteria. The TOPSIS approach requires the formulation of a decision matrix which entries indicate the performance of each alternative against each criterion. Decision matrixes were obtained from experts from the field, through questionnaires. It was found that project quality has the highest weight of 0.95, followed by project cost with a weight of 0.9. Project delivery time has the lowest weight of 0.7. TOPSIS scores of 0.5675 and 0.4781 for awarding contracts to foreign firms and combination of foreign and local firms, respectively. Awarding contracts to foreign firms is the best alternative, followed by awarding contracts to a combination of foreign and local firms.

Keywords: *TOPSIS, capacity building, contract, maritime, project delivery time*

1. INTRODUCTION

The maritime sector contributes greatly to the economic mainstay of Nigeria. The sector which is being regulated by the Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency do undertake several projects aimed at positioning the sector to effectively deliver the mandate assigned to it. The statutory functions of NIMASA include among others, indigenous capacity building (human and infrastructural capacity building) [5]. The infrastructures are projects which build should be managed to fruitful completion. Decisions taken by project managers do affect the completion time as well as the smooth execution of the project to completion. How projects in the future should be managed amidst prevailing challenges in the industry and how decisions taken can affect the project execution calls for the deployment of special tools in the analysis. Every project is time-bound; it has an execution period which must be adhered to. Turner (1998) identified five functions of project-based management which include organization, scope, time, quality and cost.[11]

Among many factors, the person in charge of the project or who is executing the project matters a lot. The competence level of the contractor based on track record plays a major role in the selection of contractors for projects. Several ways in which projects can be carried out have been identified; these include direct labour, contracting to local firms, contracting to foreign firms, or a combination of any two of the above three options. The option to go for in order to have smooth execution of the project can be predicated on a number of criteria which may include cost of the project, quality of the completed project, time of project delivery, impact of the project execution on the economy, project acceptability and other relevant criteria. To choose any of the available options of

project execution in the maritime sector of Nigeria, Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to an Ideal Solution (TOPSIS) was employed to aid in the choice.

TOPSIS is a multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) tool, used for solving multi-criteria decision-making problems [6]. The main idea of TOPSIS is to simultaneously assess the alternatives by measuring their distances to a Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) and a Negative Ideal Solution (NIS). The TOPSIS methodology and methodologies derived from the TOPSIS approach have been widely used. It has been used to solve various problems [1,7]. Several areas of applications of the TOPSIS technique were highlighted in the works of Zulqarnain *et al.* (2020) and Emovon & Nwaoha (2018).[4,16] TOPSIS was applied to power plant selection by Wang & Xin (2011)[12] while Boran (2017)[3] used fuzzy TOPSIS methodology in evaluating power plants in Turkey. Alqatqat *et al.* (2021) revealed in their research how to use Fuzzy/TOPSIS approaches to improve future forecasts for many beneficial features. Zulqarnain, *et al.* (2020a)[17] employed the use of soft set TOPSIS method in choosing the finest applicants for bank jobs. Ahsan *et al.* (2019) conducted a study in which multiple intelligence formed the basis on which student intelligence was decided and classified.[2] They used the TOPSIS method together with other methods in their study. In a study on the increasing number of diabetic patients globally, Zulqarnain *et al.* (2018)[15] used TOPSIS to evaluate the result of diabetes patients and predict groups of patients prone to diabetes. Jasri *et al.* (2017) conducted a study about employee evaluation process with the use of TOPSIS.[8] Many other studies border on methodologies derived from TOPSIS and they have been applied to various areas and disciplines [9,10,13,14]. The manner in which

contracts are awarded can be selected via the TOPSIS approach. But this has not been considered by researchers, hence, this study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

TOPSIS was applied to identify/select the most viable method based on a number of criteria or attributes. The criteria used for the selection in this work are five in number. They are (i) cost of the project, (ii) project quality, (iii) project delivery time, (iv) impact of project execution on the economy, and (v) acceptability of project by locals / host/benefitting communities. The basic steps in the TOPSIS methodology are presented below:

- Step 1: Assignment of weight to each attribute or criteria.
- Step 2: Formulation of decision matrix and normalized decision matrix.
- Step 3: Formulation of weighted normalized decision matrix.
- Step 4: Computation of Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) and Negative Ideal Solution (NIS).
- Step 5: Computation of the distance from each alternative to the Positive Ideal Solution and to the Negative Ideal Solution.

- Step 6: Computation of the closeness coefficient C_i^* for each alternative.

Assignment of Weight to Each Criterion

Weights were assigned to each criterion, indicating the level of importance of the criterion. The weights range from 0 to 1. The weights were obtained from experts. A questionnaire was prepared to get information about the weights from experts in the construction industry, ministry of transportation and ministry of works.

Formulation of Decision Matrix and Normalized Decision Matrix

The elements in the decision matrix were first obtained. The elements in this matrix represent the relative importance of each alternative with respect to each criteria. The elements generally range from 1 to 10 where 1 is of lowest importance and 10 is of highest importance. The ratings used in this work were collected as data from experts in the field. If the elements are given in form of intervals instead of single values, a normalized interval decision matrix will be formulated using the lower value and the upper value respectively. The decision matrix appears in the form of Table 1, where * in the Table denotes value to be provided.

Table 1: Appearance of decision matrix.

Criteria	Rating of alternatives					
	DL	LF	FF	DL&LF	DL&FF	LF&FF
Criteria I	*	*	*	*	*	*
Criteria II	*	*	*	*	*	*
Criteria III	*	*	*	*	*	*
Criteria IV	*	*	*	*	*	*
Criteria V	*	*	*	*	*	*

The elements in the normalized decision matrix for interval criteria input are given as in Equations (1) and (2) respectively.

$$n_{ij}^l = \frac{x_{ij}^l}{\left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n ((x_{ij}^l)^2 + (x_{ij}^u)^2) \right\}^{0.5}} \quad (1)$$

$$n_{ij}^u = \frac{x_{ij}^u}{\{\sum_{i=1}^n ((x_{ij}^l)^2 + (x_{ij}^u)^2)\}^{0.5}} \quad (2)$$

where, x_{ij}^l and x_{ij}^u are the lower and the upper interval ratings of each alternative with respect to each criterion, while n_{ij}^l and n_{ij}^u are the normalized lower and upper bounds of the interval ratings.

Computation of Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix

The elements of the weighted normalized decision matrix were computed for the lower bound and the upper bound as in Equations (3) and (4).

$$v_{ij}^l = w_j n_{ij}^l \quad (3)$$

$$v_{ij}^u = w_j n_{ij}^u \quad (4)$$

where, v_{ij}^l is the lower bound of the elements of the weighted normalized decision matrix, v_{ij}^u is the upper bound of the elements of the weighted normalized decision matrix and w_j is the weight of the j-th criterion.

Determination of the Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) and Negative Ideal Solution (NIS)

The PIS denotes the best performance of the various alternatives on each criterion while the NIS indicates the lowest performance on each criterion. The PIS is obtained by maximizing the benefit criterion and minimizing the cost criterion. Considering single value input for each criterion, the set of PIS denoted as A^+ is expressed as in Equation (5).

$$A^+ = V_1^+, V_2^+ \dots, V_y^+ \\ = \left(\left(\max_i v_{ij} \mid j \in C \right), \left(\min_i v_{ij} \mid j \in B \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

where, $v_1^+, v_2^+, \dots, v_y^+$ are the maximum values of each of the elements in the weighted normalized matrix for each alternative (irrespective of upper bound or lower bound), B is the benefit matrix while C is the cost matrix, y is the number of alternatives. The set of NIS, denoted as A^- , consists of the lowest values of each of the elements in the weighted normalized matrix for each alternative, expressed as in Equation (6).

$$A^- = v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_y^- \\ = \left(\left(\max_i v_{ij} \mid j \in C \right), \left(\min_i v_{ij} \mid j \in B \right) \right) \quad (6)$$

where $v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_y^-$ are the minimum values of each of the elements in the weighted normalized matrix for each alternative, only the benefit criterion was used in this work. The last two Equations are thus cast in the form of Equations (7) and (8).

$$A^+ = v_1^+, v_2^+, \dots, v_y^+ = \left(\max_i v_{ij} \mid j \in B \right) \quad (7)$$

$$A^- = v_1^-, v_2^-, \dots, v_y^- = \left(\min v_{ij} \mid j \in B \right) \quad (8)$$

Computation of the Euclidean Distance of each Alternative from the PIS and the NIS

The distance between the PIS and the criterion for each alternative d^+ is evaluated as in Equation (9).

$$d^+ = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (v_j^+ - v_{ij})^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (9)$$

The distance between the NIS and the criterion for each alternative d^- is given as in Equation (10).

$$d^- = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (v_j^- - v_{ij})^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (10)$$

Computation of Closeness Coefficient

The closeness coefficient C^x is expressed as in Equation (11).

$$C^x = \frac{d^-}{(d^- + d^+)} \quad (11)$$

The alternative with the highest value of closeness coefficient (value closest to 1) is chosen as the best alternative.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 2 shows the decision matrix with the weights of each criterion in bracket against the criterion. All the values here were obtained from experts (although, average values are presented). Results of the intermediary steps in the TOPSIS analysis are shown in Tables 3 to 7, while the final TOPSIS score (the closeness coefficients) are shown in Figure 1.

Table 2: Decision- Matrix with Ratings of Alternatives with Respect to Attributes or Criteria.

Criteria (Weight)	Rating of alternatives					
	DL	LF	FF	DL&LF	DL&FF	LF&FF
Cost of project (0.9)	9.5	9	7	9	8	8
Project quality (0.95)	7	7	9.5	7	9	8.5
Project delivery time (0.70)	6.5	7.5	9	7	8.5	8.5
Impact of project execution on the economy (0.85)	9	9	6	9	7	7
Acceptability of project by local communities (0.65)	9	8	6	8.5	8	8

Table 3: Normalized Decision Matrix.

Criteria	Rating of alternatives					
	DL	LF	FF	DL&LF	DL&FF	LF&FF
Cost of project	0.4585	0.4344	0.3379	0.4344	0.3861	0.3861
Project quality	0.3542	0.3542	0.4807	0.3542	0.4554	0.4301
Project delivery time	0.3366	0.3883	0.4660	0.3624	0.4401	0.4401
Impact of project execution on the economy	0.4635	0.4635	0.3090	0.4635	0.3605	0.3605

Acceptability of project by local communities	0.4609	0.4097	0.3073	0.4353	0.4097	0.4097
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Table 4: Weighted Normalized Decision Matrix.

Criteria	Alternatives					
	DL	LF	FF	DL&LF	DL&FF	LF&FF
Cost of project	0.4127	0.3910	0.3041	0.3910	0.3475	0.3475
Project quality	0.3365	0.3365	0.4567	0.3365	0.4327	0.4086
Project delivery time	0.2356	0.2718	0.3262	0.2537	0.3081	0.3081
Impact of project execution on the economy	0.3940	0.3940	0.2627	0.3940	0.3064	0.3064
Acceptability of project by local communities	0.2996	0.2663	0.1997	0.2830	0.2663	0.2663

Table 5: The PIS and NIS of each Criterion.

Criteria	PIS	NIS
Cost of project	0.4127	0.3041
Project quality	0.4567	0.3365
Project delivery time	0.3262	0.2356
Impact of project execution on the economy	0.3940	0.2627
Acceptability of project by local communities	0.2996	0.1997

Table 6: Distance of Alternatives from the PIS.

Criteria	Alternatives					
	DL	LF	FF	DL&LF	DL&FF	LF&FF
Cost of project	0	0.00047	0.01179	0.00047	0.00425	0.00425
Project quality	0.01444804	0.01445	0	0.01445	0.00058	0.00231
Project delivery time	0.00820836	0.00296	0	0.00526	0.00033	0.00033
Impact of project execution on the economy	0	0	0.01724	0	0.00767	0.00767
Acceptability of project by local communities	0	0.00111	0.00998	0.00028	0.00111	0.00111
$\sum_{i=1}^n (v_j^+ - v_{ij})^2$	0.02266	0.01899	0.03901	0.02045	0.01394	0.01567
$d^+ = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (v_j^+ - v_{ij})^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}$	0.15052	0.13779	0.19752	0.14301	0.11806	0.12520

Table 7: Distance of Alternatives from the NIS.

Criteria	Alternatives					
	DL	LF	FF	DL&L F	DL&F F	LF&F F
Cost of project	0.011794	0.0075 5	0	0.00755	0.00188	0.00188
Project quality	0	0	0.0144 5	0	0.00925	0.0052
Project delivery time	0	0.0013 1	0.0082 1	0.00033	0.00526	0.00526
Impact of project execution	0.017239	0.0172	0	0.01724	0.00191	0.00191

on the economy	7	4				
Acceptability of project by local communities	0.00998	0.00444	0	0.00694	0.00444	0.00444
$\sum_{i=1}^n (v_j^- - v_{ij})^2$	0.03901	0.03054	0.02266	0.03206	0.02274	0.01868
$d^- = \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^n (v_j^- - v_{ij})^2 \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}$	0.19752	0.17475	0.15052	0.17905	0.15080	0.13669

Fig. 1: Closeness Coefficients of the Alternatives.

From Table 2, the decision matrix shows that in terms of project cost, direct labour has the highest rating but in terms of project quality, foreign firms have the highest rating. The lowest ratings of the criteria occur for Impact of project execution on the economy against foreign firms and Acceptability of project by local communities against foreign firms. Considering the weights of the criteria, foreign firms have the highest weight of 0.95. The PIS and the NIS shown in Table 5 were obtained from Table 4 indicates that for PIS, direct labour has the highest value (0.4127) for cost of project while foreign firm has the highest value (0.4567) for project quality.

The results of the final TOPSIS scores shown in Figure 1 indicates that awarding contracts to foreign firms is the alternative with the highest closeness coefficient and appear to be the best alternative to be chosen in the absence of other

considerations. The next alternative is awarding contracts to both local firms and foreign firms combined. There is need to look at the decision matrix (and the weights of the alternatives in Table 2 critically. Foreign firms have high values in project quality and project delivery time but have low values in cost of project, impact of project execution on the economy and acceptability of project by local communities. In terms of weights, project quality where foreign firm has the highest weight. This contributed greatly to foreign firms coming on top of the alternatives. If one considers the impact of the project execution on the economy as a priority and / or project cost as a priority, these two criteria will go with very high weights (say 0.95 and above). In that case, a combination of local firms and foreign firms should be considered against awarding contracts to foreign firms alone.

Allocating projects to a combination of local firms and foreign firms has the advantage of acceptability by the local communities, will check the repatriation of funds, more intense local participation/local job creation will be feasible, and cost of projects will be comparatively lower.

CONCLUSION

Six alternatives for awarding contracts for projects execution were identified in this study. These alternatives are direct labour, awarding contracts to local firms, awarding contracts to foreign firms, using combination of direct labour and local firm, combination of direct labour and foreign firm, and combination of local firm and foreign firm. TOPSIS was applied to select the best alternative based on five

, checks repatriation of funds, and encourages local participation and job creation.

criteria or attributes. The criteria are project cost, quality of project, project delivery time, impact of project execution on the economy and acceptability of the project by the locals. Each of the attributes has weights. It was observed that project quality has the highest weight, followed by project cost. Awarding contracts to foreign firms is the alternative with the highest TOPSIS score and hence the best alternative. Awarding contracts to a combination of foreign firm and local firm is the second-best alternative. The second-best alternative could be considered as the best alternative if more emphasis is placed on the impact of the project execution on the economy. The second-best alternative also has the advantage of acceptability by the local communities

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NOMENCLATURE

- B Benefit matrix
- C Cost matrix
- DL Direct labour
- DL&FF Combination of direct labour and foreign firms
- DL&LF Combination of direct labour and local firms
- FF Foreign firm
- LF Local firm
- LF&FF Combination of local firms and foreign firms
- NIS Negative ideal solution
- PIS Positive ideal solution

C^x	The closeness coefficient matrix
d^+	The distance between the PIS and the criterion for each alternative
d^-	The distance between the NIS and the criterion for each alternative
n_{ij}^l	Normalized lower bound of the interval rating
n_{ij}^u	Normalized upper bound of the interval rating
v_{ij}^l	Lower bound of the elements of the weighted normalized decision matrix
v_{ij}^u	Upper bound of the elements of the weighted normalized decision matrix
w_j	The weight of the j-th criterion
x_{ij}^l	The lower interval rating of each alternative
x_{ij}^u	The upper interval rating of each alternative

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